

BLUE PEA FLOWER (*Clitoria ternatea*) AND LATUNDAN BANANA (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) ICE CREAM

Kae Sherinne C. Baccay, Rolea A. Reli, Lorrie Joy M. Tangcay

Abstract

Ice cream is an in-demand dessert, especially during the summer season. Consequently, in this study, the researchers innovated the popular dessert by applying blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*). Three treatments were utilized as follows: Treatment 1 (Blue Pea flower extract 64g, Latundan Banana 200g, All-purpose cream 1000g and Condensed milk 975g); Treatment 2 (Blue Pea flower extract 128g, Latundan Banana 100g, All-purpose cream 1000g and Condensed milk 975g); and Treatment 3 (Blue Pea flower extract 256g, Latundan Banana 50g, All-purpose cream 1000g and Condensed milk 975g).

The general result of the study in terms of color/appearance, taste/flavor, odor/aroma and general acceptability revealed that Treatment 2 (128g blue pea flower and 100g Latundan Banana) was the most acceptable among the three treatments. Based on the ROI, it could be said that all treatments can be profitably utilized in making blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) ice cream.

Keywords: *Blue pea flower, Latundan Banana, Ice cream*

INTRODUCTION

Food is also about climate, and weather affects our choice of food. For example, when the weather is cold, we eat hot foods like soups, and when the weather is hot, we eat cold foods like ice cream, which is very popular here in the Philippines. Every Filipino creates different types of foods that resonate with the tastes of Filipinos, such as sweet delicacies, different types of entrées, baked products, etc. But the most popular among them during the summertime is ice cream. It may be served as dessert after a heavy meal or can be eaten before a meal as an appetizer. People also like ice cream, not only because it is affordable but because it is also easy to find.

Blue Pea, also known as Asian Pigeon Wings, Blue Bell Vine, Cordofan Pea, Darwin pea, and Butterfly Pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) is an amazing brain-boosting herb native to tropical equatorial Asia. A traditional Chinese and Ayurvedic medicine, *Clitoria Ternatea* has been consumed for centuries as a memory enhancer, brain booster, anti-stress and calmativ agent. Known for its luminous indigo color, Butterfly Pea has traditionally been used as a vegetable in cooking, color deserts, or making a strikingly vibrant colored tea. Butterfly Pea is jam-packed full of health-promoting antioxidants, flavonoids, and peptides and has shown considerable promise in animal studies as a natural remedy for a range of health complaints. Many beauty

products have also been derived from Butterfly Pea because of the effects of the flavanoid quercetin on skin and hair (Bellis, M. 2017).

On the other hand, Tundan (Cebu), Turdan (Tagalog), Cantong (Misamis Oriental), Pisang Rastali (Malaysia), Pisang Raja (Indonesia), Kluai Nam (Thailand), Chuoi Goong (Vietnam), Silk Fig (West Indies) (Valmayor, et al., 2002), also very common around Manila is said to be the most common of the dessert varieties all around the Philippines. Latundan was introduced from India by a French clergyman, Letondal. Compared to Lakatan, it takes on a fatter form and pointier shape toward the end. It has a paler-hued, thinner peel (with barely any inner lining to be found). It also has a paler (almost white) flesh—within which it carries a tangier, more “tropical” flavor. Its texture is also less dense and relatively fluffier (think mashed potatoes), which also becomes more slippery and ultra-creamery as you chew (Baes, 2017).

Ice cream is a popular dessert, particularly in the summer season. As a result, the researchers experimented with a popular dessert. The application of blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) was served as a peculiar flavor to ice cream since these are abundant in many places in our country and ensured everyone, from the eldest to the oldest, could try and taste an ice cream affordably.

Statement of the Problem

This study was conducted to develop an ice cream out of Blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*). Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process of developing Blue Pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan Banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) ice cream?
2. What is the respondents' level of acceptability of the Blue Pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) ice cream in terms of odor/ aroma, color/appearance, taste/Flavor, and general acceptability?
3. What is the return of investment (ROI) in developing Blue Pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) ice cream?

Scope and Delimitation

This study was limited in testing the Blue Pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan Banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) Ice cream. This was participated by randomly selected thirty (30) respondents from Rizaluna, Alicia, Isabela.

This study used a 5-Point Likert Scale to determine the process and acceptability of Blue Pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan Banana (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana*) ice cream indicating the following criteria: odor/ aroma, color/appearance, taste/flavor, and general acceptability.

Literature Review

Ice cream may be defined as a frozen dairy product made by blending and processing cream and other milk products together with sugar, flavor, and color, with the incorporation of air, with or without stabilizer during the freezing process (Sukumar, 1980). Ice cream is both an emulsion and foam, comprising four structures: ice crystals, air bubbles, fat globules and aggregates, and the unfrozen serum phase (Clarke, 2005; Goff & Hartel, 2013).

The origins of ice cream can be traced back to at least the 4th century B.C. Early references include the Roman Emperor Nero (A.D. 37-68) who ordered ice to be brought from the mountains and combined with fruit toppings, and King Tang (A.D. 618-17) of Shang, China had a method of creating ice and milk concoctions. Ice cream was likely brought from China back to Europe. Over time, recipes for ices, sherbets, and milk ices evolved and were served in fashionable Italian and French royal courts (Bellis, 2017).

Sorbetes is still made in the Philippines today through sorbeteros, who peddle the ice cream in the streets. The sorbeteros carts are distinctly decorated like a Philippine jeepney, while three ice cream flavors are stored inside three metal canisters. Blocks of ice keep the sorbets frozen. Popular flavors or the dirty ice cream include avocado, melon, strawberry, cookies and cream, chocolate, and cheese. Now coconut milk is also used to give the sorbetes cream its creaminess. Sorbetes is scooped and served in sugar cones or in between bread buns (Upton, 2013).

Butterfly Pea or Blue Pea Flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*)

The flowers of the butterfly pea plant are quite a sight to behold. Vibrant blue or violet-hued, the little blossoms have a bright yellow slash at their centers and delicate petals that resemble the shape of female genitalia, hence its botanical name *Clitoria ternatea*. Although it can be found growing in the wild in our region, the butterfly pea is believed to have originated from South America and Asia. It is believed to have been brought to India in the 17th century then to Europe and much later to the tropics. It belongs to the sub-family Papilionaceae of the family Leguminosae and is a perennial climber. With pinnate leaves extending to five to nine leaflets, it often grows into thick foliage. But the climber is commonly cultivated for its attractive azure flowers with winged petals and light markings, which only last 24 hours. Its flat pods pop black seeds when mature (Pwee, 2004). Latundan Banana also known as 'silk' bananas, is common around Manila (and said to be the most common of the dessert varieties all around the Philippines), Latundan is said to have been introduced from India by a French clergyman, Letondal. Compared to Lakatan it has a paler-hued, thinner peel (with barely any inner lining to be found). Its texture is also less dense and relatively fluffier (think mashed potatoes), which also becomes more slippery and ultra-creamery as you chew (Vezina et al., 2018).

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Ingredients

Table 1 shows the ingredients and its proportion on the three different treatments.

In preparing blue pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) and latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) ice cream, the following utensils and equipment were used: measuring cup, casserole pot, chopping board, knife, disposable cup and spoon, electric mixer, mixing bowls, stove and wooden spoon.

Table 1. The Ingredients and Its Proportion in Preparing Blue Pea Flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan Banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) Ice Cream

Ingredients	T1	T2	T3
Blue Pea flower extracts	64g	128g	256g
Latundan Banana	200g	100g	50g
All purpose cream	1000g	1000g	1000g
Condensed milk	975g	975g	975g

Research Design

The study utilized the experimental method of research, particularly the completely randomized design (CRD), where all samples were randomly assigned. This experimental design is most associated with sensory studies to avoid or minimize artifacts due to the order of sample presentation. CRD is also an ideal design for central location consumer tests where each respondent evaluates each sample (Lawless & Heymann, 2010).

Figure 1. Process of Making Blue Pea and Latundan Ice Cream

Experimental Procedure

Figure 1 shows the process of making the ice cream with blue pea and latundan banana.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at Barangay Rizaluna, Alicia, Isabela. After which, the thirty (30) respondents were given a 5-Point Likert Scale to evaluate the acceptability of Blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan Banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) ice cream in terms of odor/aroma, color/appearance, taste/ flavor, and general acceptability.

Statistical Treatment

Results of the sensory evaluation were statistically analyzed using the one-way classification of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine if there is a significant

difference among the treatments in terms of odor/aroma, color/appearance, taste/texture, and general acceptability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Acceptability and Differences of the Treatments

Table 2. Acceptability and Differences of the Three Treatments in Terms of Odor/Aroma, Color/Appearance, Taste/Flavor, and General Acceptability

Criteria	Treatments	Mean	Desc.	C.V. (%)	LSD	Interpretation
Odor/Aroma	T1	3.20b	Highly Acceptable	20.54	0.52	Highly Significant
	T2	4.50a	Extremely Acceptable			
	T3	3.37b	Highly Acceptable			
Color/Appearance	T1	2.63b	Highly Acceptable	18.05	0.48	Highly Significant
	T2	4.73a	Extremely Acceptable			
	T3	4.33a	Highly Acceptable			
Taste/Flavor	T1	3.77b	Highly Acceptable	13.48	0.37	Highly Significant
	T2	4.80a	Extremely Acceptable			
	T3	3.50b	Highly Acceptable			
General Acceptability	T1	3.67b	Highly Acceptable	15.28	0.43	Highly Significant
	T2	4.90a	Extremely Acceptable			
	T3	3.83b	Highly Acceptable			

In terms of odor or aroma, Treatment 2 obtains the highest mean which can be interpreted as "Extremely acceptable". This is followed by Treatment 3 and Treatment 1 with means of 3.37 and 3.20; both are highly acceptable. The differences on the acceptability of the odor/aroma of the three treatments is highly significant.

In terms of color/appearance, Treatment 2 is extremely acceptable, with a mean of 4.73. Nevertheless, Treatments 1 and 3 are highly acceptable with means of 2.63 and 4.33, respectively. The differences observed among the three treatments in terms of color/appearance are highly significant.

Furthermore, Treatment 2 appears to be extremely acceptable in terms of taste/texture. This is supported by its mean of 4.80. Treatments 1 and 3, on the other hand, are highly acceptable with means of 3.77 and 3.50, respectively. Likewise, the differences observed in the three treatments in terms of taste/texture is highly significant.

Generally, Treatment 2 appeared to be extremely acceptable among the three different treatments, with a mean of 4.90. Furthermore, Treatments 3 and 1 have appeared to be highly acceptable, with means of 3.83 and 3.67, respectively. Also, the differences in the general acceptability of the three treatments are found to be highly significant. This suggests that

Treatment 2 is generally the most acceptable among the three treatments.

Cost and Return Analysis

The cost and return analysis of the different proportions of blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x M. balbisiana*) are summarized in Tables 3 and 4. Each item was computed as to the extent of production per given preparation from the three treatment samples.

Table 3. Cost Analysis of the Ice Cream Production

Ingredients	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Blue Pea Flower	7.00	9.00	14.00
Latundan Banana	11.00	5.00	9.00
Condensed Milk	100.00	100.00	100.00
All Purpose Cream	216.00	216.00	216.00
Plastic cup and Spoon	66.60	66.60	66.60
Print and Label	10.00	10.00	10.00
Labor	10.00	10.00	10.00
Electricity/Water Bill	15.00	15.00	15.00
Total Cost (Php)	435.60	431.60	435.60

It can be gleaned from Table 3 that Treatment 2 has the lowest total cost of 431.60 pesos only. Meanwhile, Treatments 1 and 3 have the same total cost of 435.60 pesos each.

Table 4. Return on Investment Analysis

Ingredients	Treatment 1	Treatment 2	Treatment 3
Total Production Cost (Php)	435.6	431.6	435.6
Unit Cost = $\frac{\text{Total Cost}}{\text{No Packs}}$	14.52	14.38	14.52
Selling Price = Unit Cost \times 50% + Unit Cost	21.78	21.57	21.78
Total Sale = Selling Price \times No. of Packs	653.4	647.1	653.4
Income = Total Sale - Total Production	217.8	215.5	217.8
ROI = $\frac{\text{Income} \times 100}{\text{Total Production Cost}}$	50	49.93	50

Table 3 revealed that Treatments 1 and 3 have the highest and same return on investment with 50 pesos. Although Treatment 2 appears to have the lowest return on investment, the difference with the other two treatments is too small.

Conclusion

In terms of color/appearance, the respondents preferred Treatment 2 and Treatment 3, rated as "Extremely acceptable," and Treatment 1 was rated as "Highly acceptable." In terms of taste/flavor, odor/aroma, and general acceptability, Treatment 2 had a final descriptive rating of "Extremely acceptable" over Treatment 1 and 3, which has a final descriptive rating of "Highly acceptable." Based on the results, the color/appearance, taste/flavor, odor/aroma, and general acceptability of Treatment 2 were "Extremely acceptable" for the respondents. After subjecting the data to statistical analysis, it further revealed that Treatment 1, Treatment 2 and Treatment 3 had a 1% level of significance in terms of the said sensory attributes. Treatment 2 was the most preferred among the three treatments. The return on investment per production of blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata x*

M. balbisiana) showed that Treatment 1 had a return on investment of 50%, Treatment 2 had 49.93%, and Treatment 3 had 50%.

The general result of the study in terms of odor/aroma, color/appearance, taste/texture, and general acceptability revealed that Treatment 2 (Blue Pea flower extract 128g, Latundan Banana 100g, All-purpose cream 1000g, and Condensed milk 975g) was the most acceptable among the three treatments. Based on the ROI, it could be said that all treatments can be profitably utilized in making blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and Latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* x *M. balbisiana*) ice cream.

Recommendations

Based on the results obtained from the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Microbial analysis is encouraged to determine the microbial content of the finished product.
2. Shelf-life analysis is advised to be conducted to determine the storage stability of the product.
3. Proximate analysis and nutritional value testing is recommended.
4. Further research is recommended to be conducted on the utilization of blue pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) and latundan banana (*Musa acuminata* x *M. balbisiana*).

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